

Theoretical Explanation and Computational Formulas for the Repulsion of Atomic Nucleus on Electrons and Strong Short-Range Repulsion

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Abstract: This paper is the fourth application paper based on the "Unified Theory of Forces," and it also addresses the lack of a comprehensive theoretical explanation for the repulsive force generated by electrons near the atomic nucleus in previous research. The main approach of this paper is to utilize the theoretical foundation of the "Unified Theory of Forces" to explain various repulsive phenomena between particles that were not well explained in traditional physics. The main conclusions of this paper are as follows: (1) The theoretical explanation for the repulsive force generated by electrons near the atomic nucleus fundamentally answers why electrons do not fall into the atomic nucleus; (2) The theoretical explanation for the elastic scattering of neutrons; (3) The theoretical explanation for the reflection of photons by objects; (4) The theoretical explanation for the strong short-range repulsive force; (5) The provision of elastic scattering mechanisms and mechanical formulas for all matter composed of electromagnetic forces. (6) Prove that the fundamental particles in the standard model of physics are composed of smaller particles.

Keywords: electron elastic scattering; neutron elastic scattering; photon reflection; repulsive force

1. Introduction

The author aims to explain the true origin of the repulsive force between microscopic particles in this paper. This includes phenomena such as the scattering of electrons by atomic nuclei [1], the ancient physics problem of why electrons do not fall into the atomic nucleus, the repulsive effect observed at close distances in the strong interaction [2], and the scattering of neutrons by atomic nuclei. All of these questions require a unified explanation: what is the origin of the repulsive force between particles at close distances.

Furthermore, this study addresses the shortcomings of the author's previous research on the "Unified Theory of Forces" [3]. In that paper, the author did not provide a physical essence or a reasonable theoretical explanation for the repulsive force between particles at close distances, nor did they provide a formula for calculating the magnitude of the repulsive force.

2. Scattering Mechanisms of Matter and Theory of Repulsive Force

2.1 Assumptions of Elastic Scattering Mechanism

Assumption 1: The energy loss $E_{missing}$ between particles with positive and negative charges is finite.

For example, we have shown that the energy loss $E_{missing}$ between a proton P and an electron e is always finite [3]. If the particles are quarks, we can similarly prove that the energy loss between two quarks with positive and negative charges is also always finite.

The reasonableness of assumption 1 has been fully demonstrated in the "Unified Theory of Forces" [3].

Assumption 2: There is no lower limit for the distance at which repulsive force occurs between particles with the same charge.

For example, the formula for the repulsive force between two electrons e is as follows:

$$-F = k \frac{e^2}{r^2}$$

So far, we have not discovered a lower limit for the distance of the Coulomb repulsive force between two particles with the same charge. Of course, Assumption 2 is a simplified ideal assumption, as particles always have a size and it is not possible to find truly infinitesimal particles.

Assumption 3: We assume that all charged particles are point charges.

We acknowledge that this assumption is also imperfect, as all matter has size, atomic nuclei are composed of quarks, and quarks move at high speeds within the atomic nucleus. However, for the sake of simplification in calculations, we make this approximation. In actual calculations, we must consider more factors.

2.2 Derivation of Formulas

Taking the interaction force F between an electron and a proton as an example, we

assume that the electron is a point-like particle (based on current evidence in physics) with a charge of $-e$, and the proton is composed of two up quarks and one down quark, with charges of $\frac{2}{3}e$, $\frac{2}{3}e$, and $-\frac{1}{3}e$, respectively.

In this case, there is an attractive force $+F$ between the electron e and the two up quarks due to the energy loss $E_{missing}$, and we assume that the magnitude of the energy loss between the electron and the up quarks is $E^0_{missing}$. At the same time, there is a repulsive force $-F$ between the electron and the down quark. Since the attractive force $+F$ is greater than the repulsive force $-F$, the electron is attracted by the proton. However, at a distance r where energy conservation is realized (the energy loss $E^0_{missing}$ is converted into the kinetic energy of the electron and proton), r is the equilibrium radius, which is given by the following formula:

$$r = k \frac{q_1 q_2}{E^0_{missing}} = k \frac{\frac{4}{3}e^2}{E^0_{missing}} \quad (1)$$

Where e refers to the charge of a unit charge, k is the Coulomb constant, and $E^0_{missing}$ refers to the magnitude of the energy loss between the two up quarks and the electron.

According to the conclusions of the "Unified Theory of Forces," when the distance between the proton P and the electron e is less than r , there will no longer be an attractive force between the up quarks and the electron, as it would result in an energy exceeding the energy loss $E^0_{missing}$, which violates the law of energy conservation. Therefore, when the distance between the proton P and the electron e is less than r , only the down quark and the electron will generate a repulsive force $-F_1$, the magnitude of which is given by the following formula:

$$-F_1 = \frac{1}{3}k \frac{e^2}{r^2} \quad (2)$$

It should be noted that the premise for the validity of equation (2) is based on the assumption that the electron is composed of a single negatively charged particle. However, in reality, the author speculates that the electron, like the proton, may have a more intricate internal structure. Therefore, the ultimate form of $-F_1$ still needs to be verified through experiments. The differences between positrons and electrons may manifest in the different compositions of their more intricate internal structures.

Through the example above, we can derive the formula for the repulsive force at close distances between two particles (where particle A and particle B can have positive and negative charges respectively, one can be charged while the other is neutral, or both can be neutral). We assume that particle A is composed of two smaller charged particles q_1 and $-q_2$, and particle B is composed of two smaller charged particles q_3 and $-q_4$. Based on the conclusions of the "Unified Theory of Forces," we assume that the magnitude of the energy loss between q_1 and $-q_4$ is $E_{missing}^{14}$, and the magnitude of the energy loss between $-q_2$ and q_3 is $E_{missing}^{23}$. The total energy loss between A and B is given by $E_{missing}^{14} + E_{missing}^{23}$. Using equation (1), we can calculate the equilibrium radius r_{14} between q_1 and $-q_4$, as well as the equilibrium radius r_{23} between $-q_2$ and q_3 :

$$r_{14} = k \frac{q_1 q_4}{E_{missing}^{14}} \quad (3)$$

$$r_{23} = k \frac{q_2 q_3}{E_{missing}^{23}} \quad (4)$$

When the distance between A and B, r , is less than both r_{14} and r_{23} , A and B will exhibit a repulsive force $-F$, the magnitude of which is given by:

$$-F = k \frac{q_1 q_3}{r^2} + k \frac{q_2 q_4}{r^2} \quad (5)$$

The above equation (5) is the underlying formula for the repulsive force between particles that we have been searching for.

It is important to note that when $r_{14} < r < r_{23}$ (assuming $r_{14} < r_{23}$), we do not consider this scenario. In this case, we only need to compare the attractive force and repulsive force between the particles to determine which one is greater.

Furthermore, during the process of mutual attraction between A and B, due to the repulsive force between $-q_2$ and $-q_4$, as well as between q_3 and q_1 , new energy loss $E_{missing}$ is actually generated. However, as this does not affect the essence of the problem we are discussing today, we have not included the formula for the impact of the repulsive force.

2.3 Discussion on the Applicability of this Theory

The repulsive force between particles mentioned above is applicable to all interactions between elementary particles composed of charged particles, including the following scenarios:

(1) It can be used to explain the origin of the repulsive force between atomic nuclei and outer electrons, providing a good explanation for why outer electrons do not fall into the atomic nucleus. It also answers the physical nature of why atomic nuclei still exert elastic scattering on moving electrons.

(2) It can be used to explain the elastic scattering of atomic nuclei on neutrons. According to current theories, it is difficult to explain why atomic nuclei can produce small-angle elastic scattering on neutrons at relatively long distances.

(3) It can also be used to explain the elastic scattering of high-speed particles colliding with atomic nuclei. We believe that the same repulsive effect can occur between tiny quarks inside the atomic nucleus, and there may be even more intricate structures within quarks. This paper also proves that the current standard model of physics is incomplete.

(4) It can be used to explain the reflection of photons. In fact, we have already demonstrated that photons are also composed of two or several charged particles. Therefore, the reflection of photons by matter is actually the elastic scattering of matter on photons.

(5) It can be used to speculate on the more intricate internal structure of microscopic particles.

(6) It can be used to explain the effects of identical particles, such as the effects of identical particles in high-speed collisions of atomic nuclei.

(7) This paper also provides a solid theoretical basis for another article of ours on the origin of planetary magnetic fields and neutron star magnetic fields [4]. This theory can be better applied in earthquake prediction, as changes in internal pressure in the Earth can lead to changes in magnetic field strength. Therefore, the author believes that it will have practical significance.

3.Limitations of this Study

We cannot provide the specific magnitude of energy loss $E_{missing}$, between any two positive and negative point charges A and B. This requires experimental detection, and the magnitude of energy loss, $E_{missing}$, between any positive and negative point charges

A and B can also be altered by the release of energy to the surroundings. For example, atoms can change the magnitude of energy loss, $E_{missing}$, between outer electrons and the atomic nucleus by emitting light.

At the same time, we are currently uncertain about the specific effects of particles exhibiting wave-like characteristics. For example, photons can undergo refraction, not just reflection.

4. Conclusion

Through the analysis above, we have essentially explained the physical nature of the repulsive forces between almost all particles at short distances that cannot be explained by current physics. We believe that this study is important and effective. It can help us better understand the physical nature of why outer electrons do not fall into the atomic nucleus, the essence of scattering of protons or neutrons by atomic nuclei, the physics behind the high-speed motion of quarks without merging with each other, and the physical nature of the repulsive forces displayed by the strong force at short distances.

References:

1. Latey C. Determination of mean drift conduction electron velocity in a conductor. *Phys Educ.* 1988;23(1):51.
2. NING Ping-zhi(2008). RECENT PROGRESS IN NUCLEAR FORCE RESEARCH AND SOME PROBLEMS. *PROGRESS IN PHYSICS(China).VOL.28.NO.4*
3. Qin S (2022) Unified Theory of Gravity, Electromagnetic Force, Strong and Weak Forces and their Applications: Theoretical Explanation for Dark Matter. *J Phys Chem Biophys.* 12:335.
4. ShengQin. 2023. "Theoretical Explanation and Experimental Design of the Origin of Earth's Magnetic Field, Stellar Magnetic Field, and Neutron Star Magnetic Field." *OSF Preprints.* April 1. doi:10.31219/osf.io/sh8rd.